

Requirement Consolidation

Deliverable 20

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About PETRI

The assessment and monitoring of microbial plankton biodiversity are essential to obtain a robust evaluation of the marine environment's health status. While the bulk marine photosynthetic plankton is a proxy for primary production, a fundamental process that supports higher trophic levels, the specific composition of the microbial community is key to unveiling a number of biogeochemical processes such as nitrogen fixation, carbon sequestration, oxic-anoxic remineralization, and ocean acidification, that provide valuable indications on ecosystems dynamics and health.

The objective of PETRI-MED is to **develop novel strategies to determine and monitor the status and spatio-temporal trends of microbial plankton community composition and function based on satellite observations**. This will permit to address the following questions of the highest relevance to both the scientific community and society in general:

- Q1. **What is the current spatio-temporal variability of microbial plankton community composition, biodiversity, and health status?**
- Q2. **How do those patterns correlate with physical phenomena such as marine currents or river run-offs?**
- Q3. **Are those patterns influenced by human-related forcing (e.g., use of land and coastal ecosystems)?**
- Q4. **Can we observe specific connections between adjacent ecosystems?**
- Q5. **Can we detect fragmented habitats or identify new potential protected zones or ecological corridors through remote sensing?**

PETRI-MED will address these questions by relying on a highly multidisciplinary approach, **combining satellite observations from both past and present missions, field measurements (optical, physical, chemical, and omics), biogeochemical/ecosystem/marine currents modeling, and artificial intelligence (AI)**.

Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to define the main requirements as well as to identify the consequent protocols and products for the fulfillment of the objectives of PETRI-MED.

Keywords

Requirements

1 Scientific Review

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Objectives: Review currently available in situ and remote-sensing-based plankton biodiversity indicators.

Phytoplankton is considered a suitable indicator for assessing the health of the pelagic habitat. Due to its characteristics, such as high growth rate and seasonal variability, phytoplankton does not respond to the same anthropogenic pressures as benthos, nor does it respond on the same temporal scale (Margiotta et al., 2020). Therefore, it can only be used as a quality indicator in conjunction with well-defined environmental conditions. Phytoplankton is generally described in terms of various characteristics such as abundance, biomass, diversity, and bloom frequency and intensity, which alone or in various combinations are to be used to assess the ecological (WFD 2000/60/ EC) and environmental status (MSFD 2008/56/ EC) of European coastal waters and open seas. Member States have committed to cooperate in the integration of these EU Directives and Regional Sea Conventions - RSC (OSPAR, HELCOM, Barcelona and Bucharest Conventions) to achieve comparable and harmonised approaches.

Experts from European regional seas gathered under the RSC umbrella have been developing phytoplankton indicators that characterise pelagic habitat with varying degrees of success. This is an ongoing process that involves phytoplankton indicator development (i.e., selection of parameters, baseline and threshold establishment), testing, and, if performing well, operationalization. There are many available reports and other literature (Magliozzi et al. 2021, 2023; Varkitzi et al. 2018a; Budria et al. 2017; Dickey-Collas et al. 2017; Lombard et al., 2019) resulting from several projects carried out on this topic since the 2000s (ABIOMMED for the Mediterranean Sea, NEA PANACEA for NE Atlantic and HELCOM BLUES for the Baltic Sea as examples of sister projects from the DG ENV /MSFD 2020 call, ANEMONE project for the Black Sea). Table 1 provides an overview of operational and under-development phytoplankton parameters for pelagic habitat assessment in European regional seas.

Table 1. Overview of phytoplankton parameters used for pelagic habitat assessment in European regional seas.

Phytoplankton characteristic	Parameter	RCS/Region	Indicator	Reference	Note
Biomass	chlorophyll-a (in situ, satellite)	OSPAR	PH2 ^a	OSPAR, 2017a	
		HELCOM	phytoplankton biomass or biovolume	HELCOM, 2018a	
		Mediterranean Sea	chlorophyll-a	Giovanardi et al., 2018; Commission Decision 2018/229/EU	
		Black Sea	chlorophyll-a	ANEMONE, 2021	
Abundance	abundance and/or biomass of lifeform pairs ^b	OSPAR	PH1 ^c	OSPAR, 2022; McQuatters-Gollop et al., 2019	PH1 relies on Plankton Index (PI) that quantifies the change of lifeform pairs
Diversity	Alpha diversity indices	OSPAR	PH3 ^d	OSPAR, 2017b	Indices can address richness, diversity, evenness, dominance
	Beta diversity indices	OSPAR	PH3 ^d	OSPAR, 2017b; Legendre and De Cáceres, 2013	Local Contribution to Beta Diversity (LCBD) index
Size	size spectra, abundance	Mediterranean Sea Black Sea	ISS-Phyto	Vadrucci et al., 2013	Developed for coastal lagoons
Seasonal succession	abundance of functional groups	HELCOM	Seasonal succession of dominating phytoplankton groups	HELCOM, 2018b	Under development
Intensity of blooms	frequency, coverage, biomass	HELCOM	Cyanobacterial Bloom Index (CyaBI)	HELCOM, 2018c	Applied in the open sea. Based on CSA (satellite derived product) and in situ biomass

^a PH2 - Changes in Phytoplankton Biomass and Zooplankton Abundance

^b lifeform pairs: diatoms / dinoflagellates, pelagic / tychopelagic diatoms, large ($\geq 20 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) / small ($< 20 \mu\text{m}$ diameter) phytoplankton

^c PH1 - Changes in phytoplankton and zooplankton communities

^d PH3 - Changes in plankton diversity

European Commission Decision 2013/480/EU, later replaced by Decision 2018/229/EU, considered chlorophyll-a as the only classification parameter for the Biological Quality Element (BQE) phytoplankton as a result of intercalibration exercise of the Mediterranean Geographical Intercalibration Group (Med- GIG). The latest EC Decision establishes threshold values for BQE phytoplankton in the coastal waters of the Mediterranean Member States. This shows that the Mediterranean Sea lags behind other European seas, especially the Baltic Sea and NE Atlantic in the operational use of other phytoplankton parameters that characterise the pelagic habitat (Teixeira et al., 2014, 2016).

Phytoplankton studies in coastal and open waters of the Mediterranean are very heterogeneous in terms of abundance, study site characteristics, sampling strategy, methodology and taxonomic identification, making it very difficult to compare large-scale seasonal and spatial patterns and cycles and to draw conclusions. So far, plankton indicators mostly refer to Mediterranean coastal waters with specific case studies, e.g., in the Adriatic and Aegean Seas, and their development is always linked to environmental pressures (Markogianni et al., 2017; Ninčević-Gladan et al., 2015; Spatharis and Tsirtsis, 2010; Varkitzi et al., 2018b, Francé et al. 2021). The ongoing ABIOMMED project has made progress in identifying the spatial and temporal scales relevant to pelagic habitat assessment based on phytoplankton functional types derived from satellite chlorophyll-a (Di Cicco et al., 2017).

Despite the fact that the use of chlorophyll-a as a proxy for phytoplankton biomass has many advantages (time- and cost-efficient and reproducible analytical methods, easily comparable results), the use of other characteristics such as diversity and abundance can provide better information about the whole community, which should, however, include pico- and nanophytoplankton in addition to those belonging to the microplankton detected by usual microscopy techniques (Domingues et al., 2008). In addition, phytoplankton biovolume or carbon biomass have been proposed to overcome the limitations of using only chlorophyll-a (Cozzoli et al., 2017).

1.1 Requirements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC)

The criteria and methodological standards for Good Environmental Status (GES) of marine waters, as well as specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment, were established in European Commission Decisions that followed the framework established by the MSFD. Compared to the repealed Commission Decision 2010/477/EU, the Commission Decision 2017/848/EU that replaced it is much more precise with respect to pelagic habitat. Plankton diversity is addressed in one primary criterion for pelagic

habitats (D1C6), where the condition of the habitat type as a whole is considered in terms of its biotic and abiotic characteristics and functions (Table 2).

Table 2: Elements of primary criterion D1C6 for pelagic habitats that relate to MSFD Descriptor 1 - Biological diversity.

Theme

Pelagic habitats (relating to Descriptor 1)

Criteria, including criteria elements, and methodological standards:

Criteria elements	Criteria	Methodological standards
<p>Pelagic broad habitat types (variable salinity⁽¹⁾, coastal, shelf and oceanic/beyond shelf), if present in the region or subregion, and other habitat types as defined in the second paragraph.</p> <p>Member States may select, through regional or subregional cooperation, additional habitat types according to the criteria laid down under 'specifications for the selection of species and habitats'.</p>	<p>D1C6— Primary:</p> <p>The condition of the habitat type, including its biotic and abiotic structure and its functions (e.g. its typical species composition and their relative abundance, absence of particularly sensitive or fragile species or species providing a key function, size structure of species), is not adversely affected due to anthropogenic pressures.</p> <p>Member States shall establish threshold values for the condition of each habitat type, ensuring compatibility with related values set under Descriptors 2, 5 and 8, through regional or subregional cooperation.</p>	<p><i>Scale of assessment:</i></p> <p>Subdivision of region or subregion as used for assessments of benthic broad habitat types, reflecting biogeographic differences in species composition of the habitat type.</p> <p><i>Use of criteria:</i></p> <p>The extent to which good environmental status has been achieved shall be expressed for each area assessed as:</p> <p>(a) an estimate of the proportion and extent of each habitat type assessed that has achieved the threshold value set;</p> <p>(b) a list of broad habitat types in the assessment area that were not assessed.</p>

⁽¹⁾ Retained for situations where estuarine plumes extend beyond waters designated as Transitional Waters under Directive 2000/60/EC.

1.2 Requirements of the Barcelona Convention

In addition to the great natural heterogeneity of the Mediterranean Sea, the geopolitical diversity of the area (EU membership vs. associated members and non-European states) must also be taken into account. The overall protection of the Mediterranean marine environment is therefore carried out within the framework of the Barcelona Convention and its Protocols, signed by 22 Contracting Parties, including the EU, which committed themselves in 2008 to implement the Ecosystem Approach (EcAp). The overarching goal is to achieve and maintain GES of the Mediterranean Sea and coasts, reflecting the requirements of MSFD through 11 Ecological Objectives (EO), divided into 23 Common Indicators and 4 candidate indicators. In 2016, UNEP/MAP adopted the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme for the Mediterranean Sea and Coast and Related Assessment Criteria (IMAP) to facilitate the implementation of EcAp (UNEP/MAP, 2016). Currently, the IMAP covers 9 of 11 EO, including EO1, which addresses biodiversity and parallels Descriptor 1 of MSFD.

In EO1, two Common Indicators relate to pelagic habitats:

1. Common indicator 1 (CI1): Habitat distributional range (E01), to include the extent of habitat as a relevant attribute, and
2. Common indicator 2 (CI2): Condition of the habitat's typical species and communities (E01).

Group of experts for pelagic habitat under UNEP/RAC/ SPA was established in 2023 with the goal of developing CI1 and CI2. Recent progress was presented at the 16th meeting of the SPA /BD Focal Points in May 2023 (UNEP/RAC/ SPA, 2023). For phytoplankton, the expert group defined the following parameters that can be used to develop indicators for pelagic habitats considering CI2:

- Biomass (chlorophyll-a, carbon)
- Abundance (by species/genera or groups)
- Size and biovolume

With respect to CI1, six pelagic habitat types have been proposed for the epipelagic layer, which can be further developed at national or/and sub-regional level. The definition of habitat types takes into account the distribution of primary productivity in terms of chlorophyll-a concentrations in combination with the reporting guidance under the MSFD. These types, with the exception of the one that includes oceanic waters with deep chlorophyll maximum, can be detected by satellite, making the proposed classification practically suitable for continuous monitoring throughout the Mediterranean. It should be emphasised that for both common indicators, work is still ongoing.

In the context of the PETRI-MED project, we see many similarities with the work of the expert group working on the implementation of IMAP for pelagic habitats. The main common goal is to **use satellite data and products both to determine total phytoplankton biomass (as Chl) and to determine PFTs (Di Cicco et al., 2017). It is important that these products are calibrated with in situ measurements of photosynthetic pigments (HPLC) or alternatively genomic analysis. The alpha diversity index is considered a convenient index for intuitive monitoring of the ecosystem status.**

The large spatial and temporal coverage of satellite data offers great potential for identifying trends in phytoplankton biomass and diversity (at the functional group level), which is one of the goals of the PETRI-MED project. Identifying trends related to environmental pressures appears to be a more realistic alternative for determining the environmental status of pelagic habitats than establishing reference and threshold values based on various indices.

Finally, the assessment of the diversity of the bacterial component of plankton has never been considered so far for the evaluation of the ecosystem status. Further development in this context may produce great benefit to characterization and monitoring of the marine environment, **effort should be put exploring the joint**

exploitation of satellite optical remote sensing, AI modelling and a set of physical, omics, and biogeochemical auxiliary in situ data.

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2 Input dataset definition: Omics and in situ environmental data

P. Galand and R. Logares

Objectives: Review available in situ data to match with the requirements defined in Section 2.1 and with the in situ data in Section 2.2. Selected data will be used as input to the AI algorithms.

Diversity within marine microbial communities is fundamental for the health and resilience of marine ecosystems. These communities encompass an immense array of microorganisms, including bacteria, archaea, and microalgae, each playing unique roles in nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, and overall ecosystem functioning. In addition, a diverse microbial community ensures functional redundancy, enhancing the ecosystem's stability and resilience and ability to withstand environmental fluctuations and disturbances. Moreover, diversity within marine microbial communities has been closely linked to ecosystem productivity. High microbial diversity often correlates with increased rates of primary production, as diverse communities can efficiently exploit a wide range of available resources.

Because of the importance of diversity for the definition ecosystem processes we chose to use it as input data for omics. More precisely, we chose the Shannon index (H') as data to define the alfa-diversity of communities. H' is measured using the following equation, where p_i is the proportion of each species/OTU/ASV in the sample

$$H' = -\sum_{i=1}^n (p_i \ln p_i)$$

As for in situ environmental data, routine surveys of marine microbial communities are often associated to measures of sea water salinity, temperature, and nutrient concentrations. These variables will be used as input dataset.

2.1 Quality control

Alpha Diversity Index is computed on 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA sequence data based on the Shannon index (H') definition. Sequence data are obtained by amplifying DNA with specific 16S or 18S primers, and the PCR product is sequenced using Illumina technology. For data analysis, sequences are used to build amplicon sequence variant (ASV) abundance tables using DADA2 (Callahan et al., 2016) in R (R Core Team, 2022). After that, samples are normally rarefied to the same number of sequences per sample to allow for reliable comparisons (Schloss, 2024). The Shannon index is computed from the ASV table using the vegan package 3 in R.

Table 3. Table showing the number of samples available as input for the different time series. BBMO: Blanes Bay, Spain; SOLA: Banyuls Bay, France; MOLA: Banyuls offshore, France; VIDA: Gulf of Trieste, Slovenia; HOTMIX: Open Mediterranean Sea.

Station	Position	Number of samples	Frequency		Start date	End date	Marker
BBMO	41.670417, 2.800167	120	monthly		26/01/2004	04/12/2013	16S and 18S
SOLA	42.488702, 3.142906	142	weekly/bi-weekly		05/01/2015	30/03/2017	16S and 18S
SOLA	42.488702, 3.142906	158	bi-monthly		26/03/2007	02/02/2015	16S and 18S
MOLA	42.4502, 3.533933333	57	monthly		21/07/2004	28/04/2011	16S
VIDA	45.548833, 13.5505	36	monthly		11/10/2018	14/12/2021	16S
VIDA	45.548833, 13.5505	23	monthly		11/03/2019	14/12/2021	18S
HOTMIX	Open Mediterranean Sea	25	-		27/04/2014	29/05/2014	16S and 18S

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3 Input dataset definition: Satellite data

M. Talone and E. Organelli

Objectives: Review currently available satellite remote-sensing data to match with the requirements defined in Section 2.1 and with the in situ data in Section 2.2. Selected data will be used as input to the AI algorithms.

Three satellite datasets are currently available satisfying the requirements identified in Section 2.1, i.e.:

OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143: a multi-year Bio-Geo_Chemical (BGC) regional dataset of the Mediterranean Sea including:

- chlorophyll concentration (CHL) evaluated via region-specific algorithms (Case 1 waters: Volpe et al., 2019, with new coefficients; Case 2 waters, Berthon and Zibordi, 2004)
- Phytoplankton Functional Types (PFT) evaluated via region-specific algorithm (Di Cicco et al. 2017)
- Remote Sensing Reflectance (RRS)
- diffuse attenuation coefficient of light at 490 nm (KD490) via region-specific algorithm (Volpe et al., 2019)
- IOPs (Inherent Optical Properties) such as absorption and scattering and particulate and dissolved matter (ADG, APH, BBP), via QAAv6 model (Lee et al., 2002 and updates)
- Integrated Primary Production (PP)

Data from SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B are used and the product is delivered daily with a spatial resolution of 1 km by the Copernicus Marine Service (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00299>)

OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L4_MY_009_144: a multi-year Bio-Geo_Chemical (BGC) Gap Free regional dataset of the Mediterranean Sea including:

- chlorophyll concentration (CHL) evaluated via region-specific algorithms (Case 1 waters: Volpe et al., 2019, with new coefficients; Case 2 waters, Berthon and Zibordi, 2004)
- Phytoplankton Functional Types (PFT) evaluated via region-specific algorithm (Di Cicco et al. 2017)
- Integrated Primary Production (PP)

Data from SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B are used and the product is delivered daily with a spatial resolution of 1 km by the Copernicus Marine Service (<https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00300>)

C3S ESA OC-CCI: a multi-year global dataset including:

- chlorophyll concentration (CHL) evaluated via global algorithms

- Remote Sensing Reflectance (RRS)

Data from SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B are used and the product is delivered quarterly with a 9- to 12-month latency behind real time, with temporal and spatial resolutions of 1 day and 4 km by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.f85b319d>)

Main Characteristics are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Satellite products for PETRI-MED

Dataset	Sensors	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Period	Variables	Notes
OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143	SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B	1 km	Daily	1998-present	Chl RRS PFT Kd490 IOPs PP	Local algorithms
OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L4_MY_009_144	SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B	1 km	Daily	1998-present	Chl PFT PP	Gap free, Local algorithms
C3S ESA OC-CCI	SeaWiFS, MODIS, MERIS, VIIRS-SNPP & JPSS1, OLCI-S3A & S3B	4 km	Daily	1998-present	Chl RRS	Global algorithms, 8- to 12-month latency

All satellite products include measurements of chlorophyll which permit the estimation of the main Phytoplankton Functional Type as well as the computation of the proposed Alpha Diversity Index; Additionally, OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143 and C3S ESA OC-CCI also include Remote-sensing Reflectance measurements, which may provide useful information to explore the possibility to retrieve information about the microbial component of plankton supported by the model outputs in Section 2.4.

Among those, C3S ESA OC-CCI is specifically targeted for climatological studies, exhibiting a higher temporal stability as result of a better platform intercalibration, but at the expenses of a reduced spatial resolution and a longer latency of the product delivery. This non-real time production may jeopardize the overall objective of effective management of Marine Protected Areas. Finally, the use of a global algorithm for the retrieval of the

chlorophyll concentration, totally in line with the application in climatological analyses, may result in a worsening performance in regional basins as the Mediterranean Sea.

Contrarily, both OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143 and OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L4_MY_009_144 show higher spatial resolution, real-time data availability and employ specifically tuned regional algorithms for the retrieval of Chlorophyll-a in both case-1 and case-2 waters. OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L4_MY_009_144 exhibits a better spatial coverage (gap-free) as result of spatio-temporal interpolation. The drawback is the missing information about apparent and inherent optical properties such as K_d490 , IOPs and R_{rs} , this latter possibly key for the retrieval of bacterial plankton diversity. **Based on the aforementioned considerations, OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L3_MY_009_143 is selected as nominal product for PETRI-MED. The application of OCEANCOLOUR_MED_BGC_L4_MY_009_144 is envisaged in case of lack of matchups, while that of C3S ESA OC-CCI is considered for future global and climatological studies.**

3.1 References

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4 Input dataset definition: Model output

A. Landolfi

Objectives: Review available model outputs to match with the requirements defined in Section 2.1 and with the in situ data in Section 2.2. Selected data will be used as input to the AI algorithms.

Microbial plankton communities encompass a wide array of microorganisms, spanning multiple sizes and key ecosystem functioning, such as nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, nitrogen fixation, ecosystem's stability and resilience. Microorganisms can exploit a wide range of available resources and respond to changing environmental conditions. Environmental parameters, specifically: temperature, salinity, nutrients, alkalinity and oxygen, are key factors that control the specific composition of the microbial community and thus provide valuable predictors of microbial plankton communities. In this context, we identified among the available model output several Mediterranean Sea products that can provide key environmental variables to be used as predictors within the AI approach. These are reported here below:

Table 5. Model outputs for PETRI-MED

Dataset	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Vertical Levels	Period	Variables	Reference
MEDSEA_ANALY SISFORECAST_B GC_006_014	0.042°	Daily / Monthly	125	2020-present	Chla PhyC NH4 DIC NO3 PO4 O2 Si ALK pH Zoopl PP fpCO2	Feudale, L., et al., 2022.
MEDSEA_MULTI YEAR_BGC_006 _008	0.042°	Daily / Monthly	125	1999-present	Chla PhyC NH4 DIC NO3 PO4 O2	Cossarini, G., et al., 2021.

					Si ALK pH Zoopl PP fpCO2	
MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013	0.042°	Daily / Monthly	125	2021-present	Temp Sal SSH MLD velocity	Clementi, E., et al. (2021).
MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004	0.042°	Daily / Monthly	125	1987-present	Temp Sal SSH MLD velocity	Escudier, R., et al. (2021).

All Mediterranean Sea models have a spatial resolution of ~4km and 125 vertical levels. Two products are available for biogeochemical parameters: Chlorophyll a and nutrients are assimilated in the MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_006_014 product which is available since 2020. The MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_006_008 product available since 1999 has been validated and tested and all parameters except for O₂ show a good fit relative to observations. Two products are available for physical parameters: MEDSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013 uses data assimilation and has been available since 2021; MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004 product has no data assimilation, and its product has been available since 1987. **Considering the temporal coverage of in situ data including a number of measurements prior to 2020, MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_006_008 and MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004 are selected for PETRI-MED in order to maximize the training/testing dataset.**

4.1 References

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